

THE ROLE OF WAQF IN REVIVING THE ISLAMIC MORAL ECONOMY IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

Senaid Zajimović

Islamic Community in Bosnia and Herzegovina – Waqf Directorate
Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
zajimovic1@gmail.com

Abstract:

The role of waqfs in revitalizing the Islamic moral economy in Bosnia and Herzegovina is of great importance for the social, economic, and spiritual development of the community. Waqfs, as charitable institutions based on the permanent allocation of property for public benefit, represent a significant component of the Islamic moral economy. Through investments in educational, religious, social, and economic projects, waqfs facilitate strengthening social cohesion, fostering solidarity, and reducing social inequalities. In the modern context, waqfs in Bosnia and Herzegovina have the potential to revitalize a moral economy based on values such as justice, equality, and sustainability. Efforts aimed at the temporary restitution and restoration of waqf properties, much of which was confiscated during the 20th century, as well as the increasing number of domestic benefactors, contribute to the development of infrastructure, education, and social protection. Through these activities, waqfs not only promote local economic growth but also revive traditional Islamic values that encourage ethical resource management. In this way, waqfs serve as a bridge between the past and the future, offering a sustainable development model aligned with the moral principles of the Islamic economy.

Keywords: waqf, Islam, moral economy, justice and fairness, social responsibility

INTRODUCTION

Islamic moral economy is a concept based on Islamic principles and values, aiming to create a fair and sustainable economic system (Chapra, 2000).

Waqfs play a key role in Islamic moral economy. They perfectly align with the principles of justice, fairness, social responsibility, and sustainability in the following ways:

1. *Justice and Fairness:* Waqfs enable the redistribution of wealth and resources within society.¹ Waqf properties or their income are used for the public good, often in education, healthcare, social services, and infrastructure, thus reducing economic inequality.

¹ The Quranic verse in Surah Al-Hashr mentions the reason why wealth needs to be distributed: "...so that it may not merely circulate between the rich among you..." (Al-Hashr, 59:7).

2. *Social Responsibility*: Waqfs provide enduring support for social projects and initiatives, ensuring that monetary endowments aimed at building schools, health and social institutions, mosques, and other public facilities serving the community and fulfilling societal needs have a lasting impact.
3. *Institutionalized and Sustainable Giving*: While zakat and sadaqah address immediate needs, waqf provides enduring resources for long-term projects. Thanks to waqf, a rich Islamic civilization was established. Even today, in Bosnia and Herzegovina, we take pride in and eagerly showcase to visitors the monumental waqf structures and the rich cultural and architectural heritage built upon waqf foundations.
4. *Ethical Business Practices*: The management of waqfs must be transparent and accountable. Responsible management of waqf properties is a core value in Islamic moral economy.
5. *Sustainability*: "Waqfs contribute to economic and environmental sustainability. Properties endowed as waqfs are often utilized in ways that ensure long-term benefits for the community, preserving resources and the environment for future generations.

In essence, waqfs are an institutionalized mechanism that enables the practical application of Islamic economic principles, providing a stable and sustainable way to support societal needs and development (Chapra, 2000).

Objectives of the Paper

1. To explore the contribution of waqfs to societal development through Islamic moral economy and their role in shaping economic, social, and cultural structures in Bosnia and Herzegovina.
2. To analyze the application of the waqf concept in Bosnia and Herzegovina, with a focus on adapting to modern economic challenges and sustainable development.
3. To evaluate the impact of waqfs on the socio-economic development of the community, including combating poverty, improving education, healthcare, and infrastructure.
4. To examine the application of Islamic moral economy principles (justice, social responsibility, sustainability) in the contemporary functioning of waqfs.
5. To identify challenges and propose strategies to improve the work of waqfs in the modern context.

6. To examine the potential for developing new waqf models that address contemporary social and economic challenges, such as poverty and unemployment.

Each of these objectives can help in better understanding the role of waqfs in Islamic moral economy and their potential contribution to modern society.

Methodology

The paper uses qualitative analysis of textual data (historical documents, legal texts, academic articles) and a comparative approach to compare waqf practices in Bosnia and Herzegovina with those in other Muslim countries. Historical analysis provided insight into the development of waqfs through different social contexts, while normative evaluation assessed contemporary management practices through Islamic principles of justice, sustainability, and social responsibility. This methodology connects the theoretical foundations of moral economy with practical recommendations for modernizing waqfs. It concludes that waqfs can significantly contribute to sustainable development through social, educational, and economic projects.

THE IMPACT OF ISLAMIC MORAL ECONOMY ON THE SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

Bosnia and Herzegovina, during Ottoman rule and even afterwards, provides a good example of the application of Islamic moral economy, especially in the field of waqfs:

Expansion of Waqfs During the Ottoman Period

1. *Development of Infrastructure and Social Services:* During the Ottoman rule, waqfs played a key role in constructing and maintaining public infrastructure, such as mosques, madrasas, hammams, bridges, hospitals, roads, and other services.
2. *Education and Culture:* Many well-known educational and cultural facilities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, such as the Gazi Husrev-beg Madrasa and Library in Sarajevo, were established as waqfs. These waqfs provided free education and cultural activities, contributing to the intellectual and cultural development of the community.
3. *Urbanization of Bosnian-Herzegovinian Cities:* Waqfs were instrumental in the emergence and urbanization of many Bosnian-Herzegovinian cities. During the formation of urban centers, the same principle was consistently applied, where waqfs played a pivotal role.

4. *Economic Waqf Structures:* Numerous economic waqf facilities were intended to support waqfs that, by their mission and purpose, did not generate financial or material value. Caravanserais, bazaars, shops, mills, and similar assets were endowed to finance religious and educational waqfs.

Waqfs After the Ottoman Period

Preservation and Adaptation of Waqf Properties: After the withdrawal of the Ottomans, waqfs continued to play a significant role in society, although they faced various challenges, including confiscation, usurpation, and nationalization of properties during different political systems. It is important to recall that Bosnia and Herzegovina, and its waqfs, have passed through five distinct political systems to date². Despite these challenges, waqf properties have remained vital in maintaining the religious and cultural identity of Muslims in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Revitalization of Waqfs in Modern Times: After the last aggression on Bosnia and Herzegovina, significant efforts were made to restore and revitalize waqfs, which contributed to rebuilding social infrastructure and supporting vulnerable groups. Alongside other organs and institutions of the Islamic Community, the Waqf Directorate actively works on reclaiming and managing waqf properties, including the restoration of religious buildings, provision of social assistance, support for education, and establishment of numerous economic projects (Ahmed, 2007).

Social Function of Waqfs

Support for Vulnerable Social Groups: Waqfs have been a primary source of social support, providing public kitchens (imarets), free accommodation for travelers, and financial aid to the poor. This practice aligns with the principles of Islamic moral economy, emphasizing care for the socially disadvantaged and marginalized groups.

Integration with Local Communities: Waqfs were often founded by local notables and closely linked to local communities, enabling better resource distribution and strengthening social cohesion. Together with the private and civil sectors, waqfs and local communities built infrastructure (Gamal, 2006).

Legal Framework and Management of Waqfs

Shariah Courts and Administration: During the Ottoman period, waqfs were regulated and overseen by Sharia courts, ensuring that waqf properties were used in accordance with the founder's wishes expressed in waqf deeds and Islamic laws. This administration was crucial for preserving the moral and economic functions of waqfs.

² The Ottoman Empire, the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy, the Kingdom of Serbs, Croats, and Slovenes, the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia.

Continuity in Management: Despite changes in political structures, the system of managing waqfs largely remained intact, enabling the long-term preservation and functionality of these institutions. Bosnia and Herzegovina has provided a good example of the application of Islamic moral economy through waqfs, contributing to socio-economic development, education, and the preservation of cultural heritage. Although waqfs have faced challenges, their impact on society remains significant and relevant to this day. It is an indisputable fact that all political systems that in any way usurped waqfs eventually failed, while waqfs outlived them (Kader, 2021).

Waqfs as a Model for Local Community Development: Since ancient times, waqfs, alongside the public and private sectors, have been represented as a model for local community development. This practice was particularly evident during Ottoman rule, where all three sectors played a role in the establishment and urbanization of Bosnian-Herzegovinian cities. Today, the laws of our region define waqfs as a model of public-private partnership (PPP), and their revival is now advocated by EU and US countries.

It is important to note that the implementation of Islamic moral economy was not perfect and did not always succeed in overcoming all the challenges and injustices of the time. Nevertheless, the practice of waqf and other elements of Islamic moral economy left a lasting impact on the social and economic development of the Balkans (Asutay, 2020).

Current State and Prospects of Islamic Moral Economy in the Field of Waqfs in Bosnia and Herzegovina

According to Rijaset IZ BiH (2023), in Bosnia and Herzegovina, waqfs continue to play an important role in societal development through various projects. Numerous examples exist, but for this paper, we will highlight only a few:

a) Waqf Directorate

1. *Restoration and Maintenance of Religious and Cultural Sites:* The Waqf Directorate manages all waqfs in Bosnia and Herzegovina and secures significant funds used for the reconstruction, restoration, and maintenance of mosques, educational institutions, and other cultural-historical and socially beneficial structures across Bosnia and Herzegovina. For example, the restoration of the Aladža Mosque in Foča, the Arnaudija Mosque in Banja Luka, and the Derviš-hanuma Madrasa in Bosanska Gradiška were financed through waqf funds. These projects reflect the fundamental principles of Islamic moral economy, such as the preservation of communal benefits and the care for cultural heritage.
2. *Social or Health Projects:* The Waqf Directorate engages in projects related to healthcare services and social assistance. The construction of two parental

houses in Sarajevo and Tuzla for parents and children battling cancer, as well as the continuous distribution of hemodialysis machines to dialysis centers across Bosnia and Herzegovina, are just some examples of social and healthcare projects. Providing healthcare support to vulnerable groups is a significant example of applying the principles of solidarity and social justice within Islamic moral economy.

3. *Educational Waqf Projects:* The Waqf Directorate has realized dozens of educational waqf projects that now function independently. Universities, madrasas, and kindergartens are part of projects built and equipped thanks to waqf funds. The Waqf Directorate places special emphasis on the realization of economic waqf projects, whose revenues fund numerous missionary activities as well as the maintenance and operation of waqf properties. These projects highlight the importance of the economic self-sustainability of waqfs and their role in building a stable social system.
4. *Collaboration Model:* All waqf projects implemented across Bosnia and Herzegovina are realized through partnerships between the Waqf Directorate, local councils (medžlises) of the Islamic Community, and other organs and institutions of the Islamic Community. This model of cooperation contributes to more efficient project implementation and promotes the values of community and trust in Islamic economy.

b) Gazi Husrev-beg's Waqf

1. *Self-Sustained Waqf:* This is a unique, independent waqf³ that finances its operations through its revenues and assists other institutions.⁴ It is economically self-sufficient and holds legal entity status.
2. *Religious and Educational Institutions:* Gazi Husrev-beg's Waqf in Sarajevo is one of the most renowned and oldest waqfs in Bosnia and Herzegovina. This waqf funds and manages the Gazi Husrev-beg Mosque, participates in financing the madrasa—one of the most important educational institutions in the country—as well as the library and other cultural institutions. These projects exemplify how waqfs can preserve religious and educational traditions and contribute to the cultural development of society.
3. *Social Assistance:* This waqf also provides aid to socially vulnerable individuals through various projects, including free meal distributions. Such

³ According to the Statute of the Waqf Directorate, Article 7, a Special Independent Waqf is an independent waqf that constitutes a significant economic entity and whose revenues can finance a specific institution of the Islamic Community in accordance with the waqf deed (*waqfiyyah*).

⁴ For more details about the Gazi Husrev-beg Waqf, visit the website www.vakuf-gazi.ba.

programs symbolize the implementation of the core principles of Islamic moral economy, which encourages fair resource distribution and assistance to the most disadvantaged.

c) Waqfs in Tuzla

Among the most notable active waqfs in Tuzla are Turali-beg's and Behram-beg's waqfs. These waqfs have progressed year after year, particularly in economic terms. Their revenues finance numerous missionary activities such as organizing religious life, maktab education, youth training, and similar activities. These projects demonstrate how waqfs contribute to strengthening the community and preserving religious and cultural values through their initiatives.

Scholarships and Educational Programs: The waqf actively participates in funding education, particularly Behram-beg's Madrasa, regarded as one of the best schools in the canton. Additionally, it provides scholarships to students from socially disadvantaged families. These programs enable young people from poor backgrounds to receive quality education, which represents a significant contribution to equality and social inclusion.

Support for Cultural Events: The waqfs in Tuzla also support various cultural events, such as exhibitions, literary evenings, and seminars, thereby contributing to the preservation of cultural heritage.

Revitalization and Construction of New Waqf Facilities: In the past twenty years, there has been evident activity in the economic enhancement of waqfs in the Tuzla area, particularly in the field of restoring and constructing new residential-commercial waqf facilities. These projects highlight strategic planning and long-term vision in the development of waqf resources. The Tuzla Islamic Community Council (MIZ Tuzla) has also established its own construction company, which handles the construction and equipping of waqf facilities. Examples of smart and strategic planning include the new facilities of Turali-beg's Waqf and Behram-beg's Madrasa in Tuzla.

Educational and Cultural Achievements: These educational and cultural projects, including four faculties, ten madrasas, a high school, 20 kindergartens, and numerous educational centers across Bosnia and Herzegovina, represent waqf wealth that future generations will proudly cherish.

d) Waqfs in Mostar

Waqfs in Mostar, managed by the Islamic Community Council of Mostar (MIZ Mostar) and in cooperation with the Waqf Directorate, contribute to preserving cultural and historical heritage and improving social life. Notable projects include the restoration of waqf facilities such as the 'Tekija on Buna' complex, Karadžoz-beg Mosque, Karadžoz-beg Madrasa, and Šarić Mosque, which are key symbols of Islamic architecture and cultural identity in this region. Revitalizing these facilities not only

contributes to preserving cultural heritage but also supports the local economy by increasing visitor numbers and utilizing local resources.

Education and Scholarships: MIZ Mostar continuously supports educational programs, including scholarships for students from socially disadvantaged families. Additionally, they organize various educational seminars and workshops for youth, encouraging the development of human resources and providing better access to education for young people, which is a key principle of Islamic moral economy.

Revitalization of Waqf Properties: Special focus has been placed on the restoration and repurposing⁵ of waqf facilities for social needs as well as their economic utility. Recent projects include the construction of residential-commercial buildings and spaces for communal activities. These efforts demonstrate how strategic planning can achieve the sustainability of waqf properties and create additional opportunities for the development of local communities.⁶

e) The Waqf Fund "Bosniaks"

The Waqf Fund 'Bosniaks' represents a unique example of how waqf funds can be directed towards education and the development of young talents. Established by the late President Alija Izetbegović, the Fund symbolizes the connection between Islamic values and contemporary societal needs (Rijaset IZ BiH, 2023).

1. *Scholarships for Students:* The Fund awards a significant number of scholarships each year, enabling young people from across Bosnia and Herzegovina to complete their education, even under difficult socio-economic conditions. A particular focus is placed on returnee communities, where the Fund provides support to elementary and high school students. These scholarships are not only financial assistance but also a tool for achieving social inclusion and equality, aligning with the goals of Islamic moral economy.
2. *Cultural and Educational Activities:* The Fund organizes literary competitions, seminars, and similar activities, promoting education, culture, and Islamic values. Such programs support the intellectual development of

⁵ The repurposing of waqf property refers to changing the original purpose for which the waqf was established, governed by strict rules in Islamic law (fiqh), and in our case, by the Rules on the Transformation of Waqf Property. According to these rules, the repurposing of waqf property is allowed only under specific conditions to preserve the purpose of the waqf and ensure its lasting benefit to the community. If it is determined that the original purpose of the waqf is no longer feasible or beneficial (e.g., due to changes in social circumstances), repurposing the property is permitted under strict conditions, such as: The new purpose must align with the fundamental objectives of the waqf and Islamic law, The repurposing must result in greater or equal benefit for the community. The decision to repurpose must be made by a qualified authority (competent institution), which, in our case, is the Board of Directors of the Waqf Directorate.

⁶ The intended length of the text does not allow us to list all waqf projects. For more details, please visit the website of the Islamic Community of Mostar at <https://medzlismostar.ba/>.

young people and strengthen their connection to cultural heritage, contributing to identity preservation and the building of a society based on moral principles.

3. *Social Projects*: In addition to scholarships, the Fund supports projects aimed at assisting vulnerable social groups, including one-time assistance for returnees and support for local communities. These activities reflect the spirit of solidarity and responsibility toward the weaker members of society, which is a fundamental value of Islamic ethics.⁷

f) Support for Vulnerable Social Categories

Waqf activities in Bosnia and Herzegovina play a crucial role in providing aid to people in need and the homeless, as well as financing institutions that care for individuals with developmental difficulties. Various social programs are funded through waqf resources, implemented by organs and institutions of the Islamic Community in collaboration with the Waqf Directorate, the Social Welfare Office, the Youth Network, the Department for Marriage and Family, and others. The Waqf Directorate, in cooperation with the citizens' association 'Heart for Children with Cancer,' has built two parental houses for children with cancer and their parents, located in Sarajevo and Tuzla. These projects represent the practical application of the Islamic concept of mercy (rahma) and solidarity, showcasing how waqfs can actively contribute to improving the quality of life.

g) Development of Local Infrastructure

Waqfs are involved in the development and maintenance of local infrastructure, including the construction of facilities, roads, water supply, sewage, and electrical systems in rural areas. These projects often have a long-term positive impact on living conditions in these communities, simultaneously promoting sustainable development and economic empowerment of the local population.

These examples clearly highlight the importance of waqfs as a key element of Islamic moral economy, contributing to the development and stability of Bosnian society through educational, social, and cultural projects. Further development of waqfs, alongside improved management and the expansion of their activities, can significantly strengthen the practical application of Islamic economic principles.

Adapting Waqfs to Modern Economic Challenges and Societal Needs

Despite their deep history and crucial role in social, educational, and religious institutions, waqfs face a series of challenges in modern times. Many of these challenges arise from changes in social, economic, political, and legislative frameworks, but there are opportunities to overcome them. Identifying these

⁷ For more information about this significant waqf established by the late President Alija Izetbegović, visit the official website of the Fund at <https://fondbosnjaci.co.ba/>.

challenges and devising strategies to address them is key to preserving and advancing waqfs in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Askari et al., 2014).

CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES

a) Legal Uncertainty and Lack of Legislative Protection

One of the biggest challenges waqfs face is the lack of adequate legal protection, as there is no specific legislative framework for managing waqfs. The legal protection of waqfs currently relies solely on the Law on Freedom of Religion and the Legal Status of Churches and Religious Communities⁸, which is the only law providing some protection for the property of religious communities, including waqfs. Article 10 of this law explicitly states that churches and religious communities have the right to acquire, possess, and manage property, with waqfs, under the Islamic Community Constitution⁹, constituting a specific type of property that can be acquired and used following legislation.

Waqf properties face serious challenges, such as usurpation, privatization, and mismanagement, increasing the risk of their permanent loss. In the post-war period, privatization of property¹⁰, coupled with insufficient administrative and legal protection of waqf facilities, further threatens the preservation of these assets. An additional problem lies in laws that are not clearly defined regarding the specifics of waqfs, complicating their protection and the implementation of appropriate administrative and legal procedures (Kader, 2021).

b) Financial Sustainability and Asset Management

Waqfs face the challenge of ensuring long-term financial sustainability. Many waqfs, particularly those reliant on income from land or other assets, encounter issues such as poor management, declining asset value, inefficient resource utilization, and rising maintenance costs. Additionally, older structures require significant restoration and

⁸ Law on Freedom of Religion and Legal Status of Churches and Religious Communities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Article 10: 1. Churches and religious communities may acquire property in accordance with the law. 2. Churches and religious communities own their property and property rights, which they freely manage and dispose of. 3. Churches and religious communities have the right to restitution of confiscated property throughout the territory of Bosnia and Herzegovina, without discrimination, in accordance with the law.

⁹ **Article 27:** The property of the Islamic Community consists of waqf assets, property rights, financial resources, and other assets. **Article 28:** The property is used by the Islamic Community for its activities and cannot be used for other purposes. **Article 29:** The property of the Islamic Community is acquired from: waqf assets and other movable and immovable property of the Islamic Community, regular contributions, zakat, sadaqat al-fitr, and qurbani, income from institutions and organizations of the Islamic Community that generate profit, economic activities, funds, gifts, wills, and other revenues and contributions.

¹⁰ Unfortunately, Bosnia and Herzegovina adopted the Law on Privatization before the Law on Restitution, which had a negative impact on nationalized waqf property. A large percentage of the nationalized waqf property was transacted as a result of this law.

adaptation expenses to meet modern standards. The problem is further complicated by a high percentage of non-viable waqf properties, especially land parcels located in inaccessible areas, which are difficult to valorize or integrate into sustainable projects (Auda, 2008).

c) Challenges in Management and Transparency

Waqfs often face inefficient management structures and a lack of transparency, which can lead to distrust within the community. Key issues include irregularities in reporting income, expenses, and investments, as well as insufficient oversight and auditing of waqf activities. An additional challenge is the failure to adhere to the provisions of the waqf deed (*waqfiyyah*) and the wishes of the founder (*waqif*), which not only undermines the principles of moral economy but also erodes the trust upon which waqf institutions have built their reputation for centuries. Such non-transparency and deviation from waqf rules directly threaten the continuity and reputation of these vital social institutions (Ashker & Wilson, 2006).

e) Increasing Competition for Resources

Competition for resources such as land, investments, and public funds is becoming more pronounced, posing a significant challenge for waqfs. They increasingly face competition from private investors and other public or private initiatives that offer similar services or benefits. While businesspeople traditionally hold waqfs in high regard, this respect does not always extend to tolerating their competitiveness in the market. Businesspeople are often willing to donate or provide funds to waqfs as grants but are less inclined to accept their active participation in the market economy. This attitude stems from the historical perception of waqfs as exclusively social organizations. However, waqfs have both the right and the obligation to engage in economic activities to ensure their contribution to society through sustainable initiatives. Thus, a conflict arises between traditional perceptions of waqfs and their need for contemporary economic engagement.

POTENTIAL STRATEGIES FOR OVERCOMING CHALLENGES

Strategies for Adaptation and Modernization

To ensure that waqfs remain relevant in contemporary society and continue contributing to the community, it is essential to implement strategic measures that address legal, financial, institutional, and social aspects.

a. Strengthening the Legal Framework and Institutional Support

Waqfs require a robust legal framework and strong institutional support to ensure the protection of their assets and improve their management. This support includes:

Specific Legislation on Waqfs: Adoption of laws that recognize the specificities of waqf properties, including clearly defined procedures for registration, management, and dispute resolution. These laws should prevent misuse and usurpation of waqf assets.

Centralization of Legal Oversight: Establishing specialized legal teams or institutions to monitor compliance with waqf laws, provide legal support to managers, and address legal issues.

Harmonization of Legislation: Aligning laws with the normative acts of the Islamic Community that address waqf properties and local needs, while adapting to international standards that enable effective management.

b. Improving Financial Sustainability

Waqfs must adapt to the modern economic context through diverse approaches to generating revenue and preserving assets:

Diversification of Revenue Sources: Investments in new sectors such as tourism, renewable energy, and technology can generate stable income. For example, waqfs could develop solar energy projects or build tourist facilities in attractive locations. Past implementations of similar projects in Mostar and Tešanj have proven to be very effective.

Commercialization of Underutilized Assets: Through leasing, selling, or exchanging inefficiently used properties, waqfs can free up funds for investment in sustainable projects.¹¹

Restoration and Revitalization of Facilities: Investing in the restoration of cultural-historical facilities can attract funds through donations, tourism, or public-private partnerships.

c. Transparency and Accountability

Increasing transparency is crucial for the trust of the broader social community and the efficient management of waqfs. This includes:

¹¹ The decision to transform a specific waqf property is made by the Council of Muftis upon the recommendation of the Waqf Directorate, following a detailed procedure in accordance with the Rules on the Transformation of Waqf Property. Articles 4 to 9 of the said Rules precisely regulate the transformation process and the authority responsible for decision-making.

Digitalization of Management: Implementation of software tools for real-time monitoring of revenues, expenses, and asset status. These tools enable transparent reporting to the community and donors.

Regular Financial and Legal Audits: Introducing mandatory internal and external audits to ensure compliance with laws and Sharia principles.

Public Reporting Platforms: Creating online portals where financial operations, projects, and investment plans of waqfs are regularly published.

d. Overcoming Challenges of Increased Competition

Waqfs face growing competition for resources in the modern economy, including land, investments, and public funds. To address these challenges, waqfs need to balance their traditional functions with the need for market participation. Strategies include:

Developing Business and Investment Models: Waqfs can invest in profitable projects that generate income while simultaneously having a positive social impact, such as eco-friendly farms¹², educational institutions, and healthcare centers. Creating Sustainable Portfolios of real estate and commercial facilities allows for stable income while preserving the core principles of waqfs.

Adapting Business Models: Educating the community and business partners on the significance of market activities of waqfs can reduce traditional resistance to their economic participation.

Promoting Social Responsibility of Waqfs Through projects that combine economic and social goals, waqfs contribute to a better perception of their role in the market economy.

Diversification of Financial Resources: Waqfs can expand their financial resources by investing in unconventional sectors such as tourism, technology, and renewable energy.

Accessing international funds and grants for socially significant projects provides additional support without directly conflicting with the private sector."

¹² An ecological farm is an agricultural holding or household that employs organic farming methods with the aim of sustainable management of natural resources, environmental protection, and the production of healthy food. These farms avoid the use of synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, and genetically modified organisms, relying instead on natural processes such as crop rotation, composting, and biological pest control to maintain soil fertility, plant, and animal health. The goal of an ecological farm is to preserve ecosystems and balance agricultural production with nature. <https://www.agroportal.hr/ekoloska-poljoprivreda/3429>. Accessed on 05 December 2024..

Innovations in Products and Services: Developing innovative solutions such as digital platforms, green energy solutions¹³, and specific tourism services enables waqfs to occupy unique positions in the market.

Focusing on sectors with lower competition, such as cultural tourism or educational programs, can reduce competitive pressure.

Strengthening Partnerships and Institutional Cooperation: Waqfs can establish strategic partnerships with the private sector, non-governmental organizations, and government institutions to jointly implement socially significant projects. The public-private partnership (PPP) system is an effective model.

Cooperation with local communities increases the sense of belonging and support for waqf projects.

Adaptation of the Legal Framework: Active lobbying for favorable regulatory changes can ensure better protection and positioning of waqfs in the market economy. Securing tax incentives for projects with social impact encourages the development of sustainable initiatives.

Strategies for adapting and modernizing waqfs enable them to remain relevant and efficient in contemporary society. By strengthening the legal framework, increasing financial sustainability, enhancing transparency, and applying innovative approaches, waqfs can become dynamic institutions that preserve tradition while meeting the needs of modern society.

APPLICATION OF ISLAMIC MORAL ECONOMY PRINCIPLES IN THE CONTEMPORARY CONTEXT

The principles of Islamic moral economy, such as justice, social responsibility, and sustainability, provide the foundation for waqf activities in the modern context. Through the application of these principles, waqfs can transform into dynamic and relevant institutions that not only preserve traditional values but also actively contribute to addressing contemporary societal challenges (Asutay, 2020).

1. Justice

Justice, as a cornerstone of Islamic moral economy, involves the equitable distribution of resources and opportunities in society. Waqfs can serve as a key instrument in achieving this principle through:

Redistribution of Wealth: Waqfs facilitate the allocation of assets and resources to marginalized groups, providing them with opportunities to improve their socio-economic position. Examples include free schools, healthcare institutions, and social inclusion programs."

¹³ Green energy solutions refer to the use of renewable energy sources and energy-efficient technologies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, enhance sustainability, and protect the environment. (International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), 2022).

Provision of Basic Services: By investing in education, healthcare, and affordable housing, waqfs ensure fair access to resources, particularly for those who cannot afford them. In this way, they reduce socio-economic inequalities and strengthen social cohesion.

2. Social Responsibility

Social responsibility in Islamic moral economy involves the obligation of individuals and institutions to act in the interest of society. Waqfs play a crucial role in this process:

Support for Public Goods: By financing the construction and maintenance of schools, hospitals, and cultural centers, waqfs contribute to improving living standards and creating shared resources.

Development of Local Communities: Waqfs can implement projects that directly empower local communities, such as training programs, employment initiatives, and rural development schemas.

Education on Social Values: Through educational programs, waqfs can promote the principles of social responsibility, solidarity, and inclusion among community members.

3. Sustainability

Sustainability in Islamic moral economy encompasses economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Waqfs can contribute to this goal through:

Environmentally Sustainable Projects: Investments in renewable energy, conservation of natural resources, and biodiversity¹⁴ protection can provide long-term benefits for society and the environment. Projects such as solar farms or forest conservation not only yield ecological benefits but also generate stable revenues.

Long-Term Investments: Waqfs can focus on investments that provide stable income and continuous support for social programs. This includes real estate, infrastructure, and socially responsible funds.

Promoting Sustainable Development: Waqfs can spearhead projects that link economic activities with social goals, such as social enterprises or green initiatives that employ local populations and enhance environmental awareness.

¹⁴ Biodiversity is the variety of all living organisms on Earth, including species diversity, genetic diversity within species, and ecosystem diversity. The conservation of biodiversity is crucial for maintaining ecological balance and the functioning of natural systems.

4. Modernization and Innovation

To effectively apply the principles of Islamic moral economy, waqfs must adopt innovative approaches in their operations:

Digitalization and Technology: The development of digital platforms for waqf management enables greater efficiency, transparency, and access to donors on a global scale.

Public-Private Partnerships: Collaboration with the private sector, non-governmental organizations, and state institutions can lead to the development of projects with multiple social impacts.

Education and Training of Personnel: Introducing professional development programs for waqf managers helps them understand modern trends in management, finance, and sustainable development.

5. Development of Contemporary Waqf Models

Contemporary waqfs should combine traditional principles with innovative approaches to adapt to the needs of today's society:

Social Waqfs: Focusing on addressing specific issues such as poverty, unemployment¹⁵, and education through direct interventions.

Ecological Waqfs: Projects dedicated to environmental protection, promoting renewable energy, and preserving natural resources.

Combined or Hybrid Models¹⁶: A combination of profitable investments and social activities ensures financial stability and continuous contributions to the community.

The application of Islamic moral economy principles ensures that waqfs remain relevant and effective in contemporary society. Through justice, social responsibility, sustainability, and innovation, waqfs can actively contribute to addressing societal challenges, promoting the common good, and preserving moral values. The modernization of waqfs, while maintaining their traditional principles, is crucial for their future role as pillars of sustainable development and social solidarity.

¹⁵ The Islamic Community has implemented a significant number of waqf projects over the past fifteen years, through which it has provided employment for a large number of unemployed individuals.

¹⁶ Hybrid waqfs are a combination of traditional waqf principles and modern economic practices. Revenue is generated through commercial activities or investments and then used for socially beneficial purposes such as education, healthcare, and social assistance. The goal is to ensure self-sustainability and enhance social impact.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Waqfs are carriers of moral economy through the redistribution of wealth and resources, reduction of socio-economic inequalities, and support for shared interests. Their role in promoting justice, fairness, and social responsibility reflects the fundamental values of Islamic moral economy, making them indispensable factors in societal development.
2. The lack of an adequate legal framework hinders the consistent application of moral economy principles, such as transparency, accountability, and ethical governance. Historically, waqfs have successfully withstood political changes, demonstrating their resilience and adaptability as a model of ethical development.
3. Contemporary challenges, such as market competition and legal uncertainty, also present opportunities for innovation. Adapting waqfs to modern needs ensures that moral economy remains relevant, securing the sustainability and continuity of their socio-economic functions.
4. Through investments in education, healthcare, and infrastructure, waqfs continue to promote principles of social responsibility and sustainability. In this way, they directly ensure the well-being of the most vulnerable members of society, fulfilling the core objectives of moral economy.

Waqfs are not only historical symbols of solidarity and social justice but also crucial instruments for the practical application of Islamic moral principles. Their value in the modern context lies in their ability to adapt to contemporary challenges while preserving the core values of justice, sustainability, and social responsibility. The revitalization of waqfs in Bosnia and Herzegovina has the potential to strengthen economic, cultural, and social development while serving as a model of collective action for creating a more just society.

The future of waqfs depends on timely recognition of their role in development policies aligned with the principles of Islamic moral economy. Their modernization and protection not only ensure the continuity of tradition but also enable waqfs to become relevant and dynamic drivers of sustainable development. By strengthening the legislative framework, ensuring transparency in management, diversifying income sources, and actively involving the community, waqfs can continue linking the past with the future, providing a sustainable and inclusive model for societal development.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmed, H. (2007). *Waqf-based microfinance: Realizing the social role of Islamic finance*. *World Bank Journal*.
2. Ali, Abdullah Yusuf (1946) *The Holy Qur`ān: Text, Translation and Commentary*, American International Printing Company, Washington, D.C.

3. Ariff, M., & Iqbal, M. (2011). *The foundations of Islamic banking: Theory, practice and education*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
4. Askari, H., Iqbal, Z., Krichene, N., & Mirakhor, A. (2014). *Introduction to Islamic economics: Theory and application*. Wiley.
5. Asutay, M. (2020). *Islamic moral economy: A study of Islamic money and financial instruments*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
6. Auda, J. (2008). *Maqasid al-Shariah as philosophy of Islamic law: A systems approach*. International Institute of Islamic Thought (IIIT).
7. Chapra M. Umer, (1995): *Islam and the Economic Challenge*, The Islamic Foundation and The International Institute of Islamic Thought.
8. Chapra, M. U. (2000). *The Future of Economics: An Islamic Perspective*. Leicester: The Islamic Foundation.
9. El-Ashker, A. A., & Wilson, R. (2006). *Islamic economics: A short history*. Brill.
10. El-Gamal, M. A. (2006). *Islamic finance: Law, economics, and practice*. Cambridge University Press.
11. El-Sheikh, S: Islam's moral economy: a fiqhiconomic interpretation. St. Francis Xavier University, Antigonish, NS, Canada, B2G 2W5.
12. Encyclopaedia of Islam, New Edition: Vol. I - XI, Academic Publishers Brill, Leiden.
13. Kader, H. (2021): Human well-being, morality and the economy: an Islamic perspective Islamic Finance, Hamad Bin Khalifa University, Doha, Qatar.
14. Odluka o izmjeni i dopuni Statuta Vakufske direkcije, 2017. godine.
15. Ustav Islamske zajednice u Bosni i Hercegovini, izmjene i dopune (2014).
16. Vakufska direkcija Islamske zajednice u BiH (2020). *Izveštaj o stanju i izazovima vakufske imovine u Bosni i Hercegovini*. Sarajevo: Vakufska direkcija Islamske zajednice.
17. www.agroportal.hr.
18. www.fondbosnjaci.co.ba/.
19. www.vakuf-gazi.ba.
20. Zakon o slobodi vjere i pravnom položaju crkava i vjerskih zajednica, Bosna i Hercegovina (2004).
21. صلاح، علي. (2015). *الاقتصاد الإسلامي بين الأصالة والمعاصرة*. عمان: دار الفكر. (Salah, Ali. (2015). *Al-Iqtisad Al-Islami Bayn Al-Asalah wa Al-Mu'asirah*. Amman: Dar Al-Fikr.)
22. عبد المنان، محمد. (2008). *نظرية الاقتصاد الإسلامي: دراسة تحليلية نقدية*. القاهرة: دار السلام. (Abdul Manan, Muhammad. (2008). *Nazariyat Al-Iqtisad Al-Islami: Dirasah Tahliliyah Naqdiyah*. Cairo: Dar Al-Salam.)
23. المهندس، عبد الرحمن. (2010). *الاقتصاد الإسلامي: أسس ومبادئ*. جدة: دار الشروق. (Al-Mahmoud, Abdul Rahman. (2010). *Al-Iqtisad Al-Islami: Usus wa Mabadi'*. Jeddah: Dar Al-Shorouk.)